

Modified OET Rubric for Measuring English History-Taking Skills of EFL Medical Undergraduates: LCM Rubric Version 1

Linguistic Criteria (L)

Linguistic Criteria 1 (L1): Intelligibility

Choose the most appropriate one.

- Easily understood without any strain for the listener
- Easily understood with minimal strain for the listener
- Easily understood most of the time with some strain for the listener
- Difficult to understand with serious strain for the listener
- Often unintelligible
- Almost entirely unintelligible

Linguistic Criteria 2 (L2): Fluency

Choose the most appropriate one.

- Completely fluent at normal speed
- Fluent at normal speed, with only occasional repetition or self-correction
- Uneven flow, with some repetition, especially in longer utterances
- Very uneven. Frequent pauses and repetitions indicate searching for words or structures
- Extremely uneven. Long pauses, numerous repetitions and self-corrections make speech difficult to follow
- Impossible to follow, consisting of isolated words and phrases and self-corrections, separated by long pauses

Linguistic Criteria 3 (L3): Appropriateness of Language

Choose the most appropriate one.

- Entirely appropriate register, tone and lexis for the context
- Mostly appropriate register, tone and lexis for the context
- Generally appropriate register, tone and lexis for the context
- Some evidence of appropriate register, tone and lexis for the context
- Mostly inappropriate register, tone and lexis for the context
- Entirely inappropriate register, tone and lexis for the context

Linguistic Criteria 4 (L4): Resources of Grammar and Expression

Choose the most appropriate one.

- Wide range of grammar and vocabulary used accurately and flexibly
- Occasional errors in grammar or vocabulary, which are NOT intrusive
- Inaccuracies in vocabulary and grammar, which are sometimes intrusive
- Persistent inaccuracies, which are intrusive
- Very limited resources of vocabulary and grammar, even in simple sentences
- Limited in all respects

Clinical Communication Criteria (C)

Clinical Communication Criteria 1 (C1): Relationship Building

Check ALL of the items that apply to the student.

- Initiating the interaction appropriately (greeting, introductions, nature of interview)
- Demonstrating an attentive and respectful attitude
- Adopting a non-judgmental approach
- Showing empathy for feelings/predicament/emotional state

Clinical Communication Criteria 2 (C2): Understanding & Incorporating the Patient's Perspective

Check ALL of the items that apply to the student.

- Eliciting and exploring the patient's ideas/concerns/expectations
- Picking up on the patient's cues

Clinical Communication Criteria 3 (C3): Providing Structure

Check ALL of the items that apply to the student.

- Sequencing the interview purposefully and logically
- Signposting changes in topic

Clinical Communication Criteria 4 (C4): Information Gathering

Check ALL of the items that apply to the student.

- Facilitating the patient's narrative with active listening techniques, minimizing interruption
- Using initially open questions, appropriately moving to closed questions
- NOT using compound questions/leading questions
- Summarizing information to encourage correction/invite further information

Medical Interview Criteria (M)

Medical Interview Criteria 1 (M1): Patient Safety

Check ALL of the items conducted by the student.

- Self introduction
- Confirming the patient's full name
- Confirming the patient's date of birth
- Getting consent from the patient

Medical Interview Criteria 2 (M2): Medical History Components

Check ALL of the items that apply to the student.

- Asked about the History of Present Illness
- Asked about the Past Medical History
- Asked about Medications
- Asked about Allergies
- Asked about the Family History
- Asked about the Social History
- Asked Review of Systems (due to the exam time limit, if the student asks about a few systems, that would be considered as ROS being asked)

Medical Interview Criteria 3 (M3): Comprehensiveness of History of Present Illness (HPI)

Choose the most appropriate one

- Obtained comprehensive information about HPI to make adequate differential diagnosis
- Obtained sufficient information about HPI but not enough to make adequate differential diagnosis
- Obtained minimally required information about HPI but not enough to make differential diagnosis
- Failed to obtain minimally required information about HPI

Global Rating (G)

Global Rating 1 (G1)

Check ALL of the items that apply to the student.

- Student demonstrated patient-centered medical interview
- Student showed respect towards the patient
- Student built rapport with the patient
- Student performed the medical interview in a professional manner

Global Rating 2 (G2)

Specifically intended for evaluators who are teaching at medical schools in English-speaking countries

Choose the most appropriate one.

- At the level of an excellent student in my institution who has finished the core clinical clerkships
- At the level of an average student in my institution who has finished the core clinical clerkships
- At the level of an average student in my institution who is midway through the core clinical clerkship
- At the level of an average student in my institution who has just started the core clinical clerkship
- At the level of an average student in my institution who has not started the core clinical clerkship